

ARTS

SOUNDSCAPE IN MUSIC AND MUSIC IN SOUNDSCAPE

Chabashvili Eka,

Doctor of Musical Arts,

Associate Professor of Vano Sarajishvili Tbilisi State Conservatoire,

8/10 Griboedov str., 0108, Tbilisi, Georgia

Asitashvili Joni

Doctoral student of Vano Sarajishvili Tbilisi State Conservatoire,

8/10 Griboedov str., 0108, Tbilisi, Georgia

Abstract

The acoustics of nature gave people many musical ideas, and people enriched musical features and performance skills with the ability of a person to imitate the surrounding sound effects. Imitating and studying the audio nature, man learned to create instruments, and over time, based on instrumental modifications and many different, artificially created rules, he developed a variety of sounds (including electronic music) and principles of the different type of the composition techniques. With this approach, music moved away from its real environment and, as a result of the formation of aesthetic norms by a human, was separated from the general sound of the universe. The true echo of this problem is a question and suggestion of the famous 20th century Italian composer Ferruccio Busoni: "How can music return to its primitive, natural essence? ... Let us free it from architectonic, acoustic, and aesthetic dogmas;" [3]

Since 2023 a group of research-composers from the Vano Sarajishvili Tbilisi State Conservatoire - Maka Virsaladze, Alexander Chokhnelidze, Joni Asitashvili under the leadership of Eka Chabashvili - inspired by the above-mentioned question, are trying to answer F. Busoni through the artistic research "*Specifics of composing and performing eco-music works created for 'Sound Oasis'*". This project is carried out within the framework of the fundamental research "*Implementation of Ecomusicology Research Methodology for the Study of the Georgian Music Ecosystem*" [FR-22-8174] conducted by them, which is funded by Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG). Consultant of the project is American musicologist Aaron S. Allen, who is the author of various books about ecomusicology.

In the music of the 20th and 21st centuries, there is a growing interest in environmental sounds. Many composers of this period incorporate recorded environmental sounds into their music or imitate sounds of nature using the different effects of the instruments. The main goal of the Georgian researchers is to create a modern compositional method to compose an eco-music piece, where an artificial source of music (recording, instrument) interacts with live ambient sound, which is incorporated into the texture of the piece. They are studying the eco-system of the urban and suburban soundscape in Georgia and are looking for the ways to restore the principles of the approach of the peoples of ancient culture to music, when sound of the environment was introduced into the music. Mentioned composers studied the soundscape of one of the Sound Oasis and found compositional methods to include its acoustical features and environmental sounds in the texture of the piece composed specifically for the selected Sound Oasis. We present to you compositional methods of eco-musical work - an interactive experimental performance "Let's Listen to the Cave", created as a result of the research; it took place in an alternative concert space - the Cave of Prometheus, which the researchers called "Oases of Sound";

Keywords: ecomusicology, ecomusic, sound oasis, soundscape, composition technique, Georgian composers, interaction, cave, performance

The sound environment and music itself are part of the Earth's ecosystem. Therefore, researching its positive or negative impact is important for a clean and healthy environment. Studying the music ecosystem is a major challenge in many countries of the civilized world today. It is the reason why in the 21st century, a

new direction –Ecomusicology–has emerged in the field of musical art to study the sound ecosystem and various issues related to it.

According to the American researcher Aaron S. Allen: "Ecomusicology considers the interconnections between music, culture, and nature". [1]

Pic.1. Postulates of Ecomusicology

“The term has not been around for very long, but the idea of connecting these concepts goes back at least as far as the ancient Greeks. I found the first use of the term in 1972, but it did not start gaining traction until the first decade of the twenty-first century. In 2010 I was asked to write a definition for the ‘Grove Dictionary of American Music’¹, but given the newness of the field and the centuries-long interest in the topic, and given the numerous related concepts in soundscapes, acoustic ecology, and romanticism, and given my own critical take on the term itself, it was, I must say, a challenging task”. – as mentioned by Allen. [2]

In the 70s of the 20th century, scientists from various fields in North America and Scandinavian countries were interested in the study of the sound environment. Canadian composer Raymond Murray Schafer coined the term "Soundscape", he viewed the world as a kind of musical instrument with ever-renewing tuning. The Working Group ISO/TC 43.SC1 was established in 1981 to study the “acoustic environment as perceived or experienced and/or understood by people in context”² and began discussing a standardization method for assessing soundscape quality. It can be said that there is a natural sound, including the sound field of the Earth, from which the “music of nature” is constructed. The sound environment has a distinct evolution/variability factor that Schafer described as the transition from Hi-Fi to Lo-Fi³ Soundscape. “The country is generally more hi-fi than the city; night more than day” – as has been argued by Schafer. [5]

Georgian composer Nodar Mamisashvili (1930-1922), who established the "Sound Ecology Center" in the 90s, investigated similar issues in Georgia. In his book “Mystical Anatomy,” The author issues a significant warning, “And another great warning: think about ecology! Think about the salvation of man!” [4]

Some composers of the twentieth century tried to use the resources of the sound of nature to create music. Individual composers studied the sounds of the bio-

sphere with great interest and used them in their creations. Let's recall the famous French composer Olivier Messiaen's catalog of exotic birds - the collection he devoted a significant amount of his life to. When it became possible to record natural sounds on tape, the music gained a lot of fresh sounds. The recording of ambient noise and its use as the main musical material gave the beginning to a new musical direction "Musique concrète". Starting from "The Art of Noises" ("L'Arte dei Rumori") by Luigi Russolo and up to the present day, the study of the phenomenon of noise and the possibility of including it as musical material in a work of art is a topical issue.

The interest of 21st century composers in environmental sounds is growing. For example, the composer and sound artist Devid Stalling recorded the low-frequency signals inaudible to the human ear. The recordings include the ocean-wave-generated vibrations within the secondary microseism and the seismic signals from road traffic and industrial activity. The composer accelerated them by 120 times and the audio presents a busy symphonic soundscape, where the continuous vibrations of machines are transformed into tones of musical quality. Today including the soundscape audio material into the piece is a popular way of composing the music.

Since 2023 a group of Georgian composers - Maka Virsaladze, Alexander Chokhoniidze, Joni Asitashvili under the leadership of Eka Chabashvili – conduct fundamental research “Implementation of Ecomusicology Research Methodology for the Study of the Georgian Music Ecosystem”. The goal of researchers is, to study the sound ecosystem of Georgia through the artistic research “Specifics of creating and performing Eco-music artworks for the 'Sound Oases'” for composing an ecomusical works. They are trying to create a modern compositional method to compose an eco-music piece, where an artificial source of music (recording, instrument) interacts with live ambient sound, which is incorporated into the texture of the piece.

¹ Allen A.S., “Ecomusicology.”

² International Standard Organization (ISO) Acoustics Soundscape Part 1: Definition and Conceptual Framework. ISO; Geneva, Switzerland: 2013. ISO/DIS 12913-1-2013.

³ Sounds Like Noise. <https://soundslike-noise.org/2013/10/13/listening-to-lo-fi-and-hi-fi-acoustic-environments/>

Eco music is a new direction in music, the exact definition of which has not yet been clearly established. In 2005 Polish composer Grażyna Pstrokońska-Nawratil published an article entitled „Ekomuzyka” [ecomusic], in which she explained the term ecomusic as music created under the inspiration of the nature – art that is human-friendly and inspired by nature. In her opinion, ecomusic is not a new trend, but it has been present since the very beginning of music history. In her article she mentions about three main sources of inspiration for such music – birds, water and the cosmos.

Georgian composers' definition of the term Ecomusic is different, in their opinion ecomusical is work, where an artificial source of music (recording, instrument) interacts with live ambient sound, which is incorporated into the texture of the piece.

There was a period when only the human voice was part of the soundscape to create musical 'Artwork'. The acoustics of nature gave people many musical ideas, and people enriched musical features and performance skills with the ability of a person to imitate the surrounding sound effects. For example, a population surrounded by mountains invented the technique of antiphonal singing, which mimics the effect of an echo. Imitating and studying the audio nature, man learned to create instruments, and over time, based on instrumental modifications and many different, artificially created rules, he developed a variety of sounds (including electronic music) and principles of the different type of the composition techniques. With this approach, music moved away from its real environment and, as a result of the formation of aesthetic norms by a human, was separated from the general sound of the universe.

The true echo of this problem is a question "How can music return to its primitive, natural essence? mentioned by Ferruccio Busoni a century ago in the book "New Esthetic of Music." [3] According to the famous Italian composer, theoretician and pianist of the early twentieth century Busoni, the world sounds like music and people should be in harmony with it. Georgian composer, inspired by the above-mentioned question, are trying to answer F. Busoni within the framework of the artistic research. Busoni continues his text "... let us free it (music) from architectonic, acoustic, and aesthetic dogmas." [3] And the question arises:

Is it possible to call the source of the audible ecosystem "Music" without architectonics, acoustics, and aesthetics? Of course **NO**, but it is possible to look for the ways to restore the principles of the approach of the peoples of ancient culture to music, when the sound of the environment was introduced into the music. Currently, researchers are studying the ecosystem of the urban and suburban soundscape in Georgia and are exploring the ambient sound of environments to discover "Sound Oases" - an environment with a specific sound of the ecosystem to use in the musical piece as an instrument.

Several methods of composing ecomusic:

- Music composed especially for performing in an alternative concert space called "Sound Oases".
- Music, when the composer uses the soundscape of "Sound Oasis" as an instrument.
- Music as a "Ritual", built on the hidden bioenergy of the performers, when the sound landscape arises after the free improvisation of people who do not know each other, who play music together without prior rehearsals.
- Music that describes the soundscape of the non-human world, macro, micro or nano, even the imaginary expression of their thoughts and habits; also the perception of reality by animals, birds, fish, insects, plants, etc.

A practical way to create an ecomusic composition: find an artificial sound source (instrumental or electronic) for the piece that will blend into the soundscape.

Philosophical view of ecomusic – Creation of composition, the sound of which is in harmony with the vibrations of man, nature, environment and micro or macrocosm as a whole; as well as the possibility in the future to develop the ability to transform and comprehend the information received by these vibrations (as knowledge) at the level of thought.

A group of above-mentioned Georgian composers have got permission from the organisation "Agency of Protected Areas" in Georgia, to conduct the expeditions for studying the soundscape of Caves in Imereti region; they visited different adapted for tourists and wild caves.

Main methods of the research were:

- To study acoustic features of the location;
- Classification of the audio source, their location, timbral character. (For example, is it stable source and make pulsation like drop of water in cave? or it is mobile and aleatoric, like birds, wind in the forest);
- To look for the natural formations (like stones, wood, etc.) that can produce a musical sound;
- Notation the audio source of the soundscape in the verbal, graphical or ordinary score. For studying the sound reproduction in space and time, to realize, how the musical texture is built;
- Spectral analysis of the recorded sounds to study, what sound features are typical for researching environment, to use this knowledge for composing the el.music or instrumental music, which will be ecological and safe for inhabitants of the location and don't damage the biosphere;
- To look for instrumental timbre, pitch and rhythm analogies of the cave sounds;
- To study the sound perceiving factors of the inhabitants, what frequencies they hear and how they listen to around sound, what dynamic is comfortable and what is dangerous; (for example, troglobionts and stygobionts, animals living in Georgian caves, have specially developed antennae equipped with sensitive apparatus, they perceive low frequencies and they are

sensitive to noise because it is used to a quiet environment)⁴;

- To observe how climate and seasons change sounds, etc.

After exploring the soundscapes of the several caves, Georgian composers selected the "Prometheus Cave", where is very interesting acoustical atmosphere

Pic.2. Prometheus Cave. Group of Georgian researchers: Eka Chabashvili, Alexander Chokhnelidze, Joni Asitashvili, Nino Jvania, Maka Virsaladze.⁶

Prometheus Cave is located in Tskaltubo municipality, village Kumistavi (west Georgia). There are 22 halls found, where just 6 halls are open for tourists. It is possible to walk through the length of 1420 meters in the cave's territory visit the halls and enjoy boat tour by walking the river. Discover real masterpieces of nature - stalactites and stalagmites at Prometheus Cave, which are the most beautiful forms created by nature.

The Sound Performance included all main halls of cave (named as Argonauts, Kolkheti, Medea, Love, Prometheus, Iberia) and the beautiful tunnels connected the halls. Instrumentalists were walking near the visitors and played some musical phrases for hearing the acoustic features of cave; Visitors could listen to researcher-composers' electronic and instrumental small ecomusical compositions in the halls. Researchers discovered the natural instrument in cave; some Helictites (thin sticks of calcite (calcium carbonate) that grow out from cave walls and ceilings) have percussion instrumental sound with different pitches. So visitor had opportunity to hear cave instrument's sound also, which was named by the composers "Helictophones" and was included as instrument in mentioned pieces.

A performance leader Pianist Nino Jvania - Guide-performer - was constructing the musical form of the performance. She explained the rules of tour to the visitors, gave them tempo of walking (1step=1second), etc; but main rule for visitors was to be quiet and listen to the silence; Guide-performer controlled visitors behaviour, she stopped them to hear cave's noises or turns on them in improvisation process (as interactive activ-

ity) and audio sources for composing the ecomusical artworks. They decided to award it the title of "Sound Oasis" and on 08.10.2023 they held an Experimental interactive sound performance "Let's Listen to Caves"⁵.

ity) and conducted performers, she gave them some different signals - when they have to play or interrupt playing. This project could be considered as contemporary round dance, a long improvisation and interactive sound activities with nature, it is particular type of tour with art therapy, where everyone can participate in an artistic process.

Conclusion

The music ecosystem is a set of multi-parametric data that needs to be studied in different ways, but research focused on the ecology of ambient sound is one of the important ones for the future of humanity. Therefore, it is significant the creation of the correct forms for including environmental sound in artworks and performing art. Might be to take into account the ecology of environmental sound when composers create ecomusic pieces, on the one hand, for co-sounding with the Earth's sound resource, on the other hand, for safe interaction with the listener.

Many composers of the 20th or 21st century incorporated ambient sounds into their music as transformed it into musical material - soundscape in music.

According to Georgian research-composers, the goal of ecomusic should be to create a composition in which an artificial source of music (recording, instrument) interacts with live ambient sound and is included in the texture of the work – music in soundscape. In this case, the ecomusical composition must be performed at alternative concert venues, called "Sound Oases", perhaps at a different time than usual (for example, at 6 am) and the performance of the composition will also

⁴https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342165014_Biodiversity_from_caves_and_other_subterranean_habitats_of_Georgia_USA/figures?lo=1#fullTextFileContent

⁵ Eco-Music Club:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yHZSJeo7Dp8>

⁶ Photo of Nino Iashvili

be considered a change in weather (for example, the sound of rain during a concert), etc.

The most interesting examples of ecomusic are the round dances, which were already created in the BC era. In round dances people would feel the united energy. This urge to get united revealed itself in our age too, manifesting itself in a variety of social media. The virtual world, however, is not enough for a healthy interaction and we need to create “contemporary round dances”, like sound performance in Prometheus Cave, where people feel and share energy of each other and care the Earth.

Funding

This article is an output of the fundamental research project “*Implementation of Ecomusicology Research Methodology for the Study of the Georgian Music Ecosystem*”. The project, as well as this work, is supported by the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG) [grant number FR-22-8174].

References

1. Allen, Aaron S (2011). Ecomusicology: Eco-criticism and Musicology. In: Journal of the American Musicological Society, 64 (2), 391-394.
2. Allen Aaron S., Jeff Todd Titon, and Denise Von Glahn (2014). Sustainability and Sound: Ecomusicology Inside and Outside the Academy. Accessed 21 September 2022 from the Music and Politics, Volume VIII, Issue 2, Summer 2014 Online Content, <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/m/mp/9460447.0008.205/--sustainability-and-sound-ecomusicology-inside-and-outside?rgn=main;view=fulltext>
3. Busoni, Ferruccio (1911). Sketch of a New Esthetic of Music. New York: G. Schirmer Books, translated by Dr. Theodore Baker.
4. Mamisashvili, Nodar (2023). Mystical Anatomy. Univeral, Tbilisi, p.11
5. Schafer, Raymond Murray (1973). The Music of the Environment. In: Audio Culture: Readings in Modern Music. Continuum Int.; New York, p.p.29–39.